

MULTI-SCALE MODELING FOR PREDICTING THE VISCOELASTIC BEHAVIORS OF 3D BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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Keywords: 3D braided composites, Multi-scale modeling, Viscoelastic behavior, Relaxation stress

ABSTRACT

A new alternative calculation procedure was presented to characterize the time-dependent viscoelastic behaviors of resin-based 3D braided composites by extending the multiscale asymptotic expansion homogenization analysis method and multiphase finite element approach. The present investigation was performed based on the micro-scale fiber/matrix, the meso-scale unit cell and the macro-scale homogeneous composite. The effective viscoelastic properties of 3D braided composites were calculated in the Laplace transformed domain and numerically inverse-transformed into the time domain. The results were compared with the numerical data available in the literature to demonstrate the accuracy and reliability of the present approach. Furthermore, the effects of braiding parameters and relaxation time on the viscoelastic properties of 3D braided composites were studied. In addition, the time-dependent stresses of 3D braided composites under three scales were predicted.

1. Introduction

In recent years, interest in three-dimensional (3D) braided composites due to its excellent mechanical performance and increasing engineering application has been aroused. In order to take full advantage of the braided composites efficiently, safely and reasonably, many researchers have focused their efforts on the micro-structure modeling [1-3], the stiffness and strength prediction for 3D braided composites [4-6].

It is well known that most resin-based composites exhibit time-dependent viscoelastic behavior even though at room temperature. In other words, there will be much uncertainty regarding the mechanical behavior for resin-based composites in a long-term working environment. Therefore, it is necessary to investigate the viscoelasticity behaviors of resin-based 3D braided composites. Currently, many researchers [7-9] have focused their efforts on the viscoelastic behavior of 3D braided composites both numerically and experimentally. Multiscale asymptotic expansion homogenization analysis (MAEHA) method, which involves at least two spatial scales, namely microscopic and macroscopic scales were extensively applied to numerically predict the mechanical behavior and thermal behavior of 3D braided composites [10-18]. However, few studies have been investigated the effective viscoelastic response of 3D braided composites from the perspective of macroscopic,

mesoscopic and microscopic scale, and no special attention has been devoted to the time-dependent stress distributions of 3D braided composites.

In this work, a multi-scale finite element (MsFE) model including the fiber/matrix on micro-scale, the unit-cell on meso-scale, and the homogeneous 3D braided composites on macro-scale was presented based on correspondence principle. It was used to obtain the effective relaxation modulus and stress of 3D braided composites. The influences of braiding angle and relaxation time on the viscoelastic response of 3D braided composites were discussed.

2. Viscoelastic problem of 3D braided composites

In this work, two kinds of heterogeneous simulations and one kind of homogeneous simulation are included. The micro-scale fiber/matrix and meso-scale unit cell model were used in the heterogeneous simulation as well as the macro-scale whole structure composite model was used in the homogeneous simulation.

2.1 Homogenization in viscoelastic problem

The homogenization method is generally employed in the multi-scale analysis, which involves at least two spatial scales. In order to deal with two different length scales associated with microscopic and macroscopic behaviors, global coordinate is designated by x and local coordinate by y . The global coordinate and the local coordinate are related with each other by a positive real parameter $y=x/\varepsilon$.

To proceed with the multi-scale formulation, the displacements in the ε -space are expanded asymptotically

$$u_i^\varepsilon(x, t) = u_i^0(x, t) + \varepsilon u_i^1(x, y, t) + \varepsilon^2 u_i^2(x, y, t) + \dots \quad (1)$$

where the terms $u_i^n (n \in \mathbb{N}_0)$ are Y -periodic functions called correctors of order n of the displacement field, and $u_i^0(x, t)$ is the effective or overall displacement, only depending on the macroscopic coordinates x [17].

For the viscoelastic problem with a periodic microstructure, the constitutive equation and governing equation can be written as, respectively

$$\sigma_{ij}^\varepsilon(x, t) = \int_0^t G_{ijkl}(x, t - \tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} (\varepsilon_{kl}(u_i^\varepsilon(x, \tau))) d\tau \quad (2)$$

$$\int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} \int_0^t G_{ijkl}(x, y, t - \tau) \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \left[\frac{\partial u_k^\varepsilon(x, \tau)}{\partial x_l} \right] \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} d\Omega d\tau - \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} f_i v_i dx - \int_\Gamma c_i v_i d\Gamma = 0 \quad (3)$$

where G_{ijkl} is the relaxation tensor of the component materials. f_i and c_i are the body force and surface traction, respectively. v_i is the virtual displacement. Ω^ε and Γ are the solid part and the boundary of the domain Ω , respectively.

According to the corresponding principle [18], Laplace transformation is adopted to solve the time-dependent viscoelastic problem. Substituting the Laplace transformed displacements of Eq. (1) into Eq. (3), and collecting the terms with the same order of ε , the following expressions can be

obtained.

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\varepsilon^2}[M_1 u_k^0(x, s)] + \frac{1}{\varepsilon}[M_1 u_k^1(x, y, s) + M_2 u_k^0(x, y, s)] + [M_1 u_k^2(x, y, s) + M_2 u_k^1(x, y, s) \\ & + M_3 u_k^0(x, y, s)] + \varepsilon[\dots] + \varepsilon^2[\dots] = \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} f_i v_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \tilde{t}_i v_i d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where

$$M_1 = \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} s G_{ijkl}(x, s) \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y_j} d\Omega \quad (5)$$

$$M_2 = \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} s G_{ijkl}(x, s) \frac{\partial}{\partial y_l} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} d\Omega + \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} s G_{ijkl}(x, s) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y_j} d\Omega \quad (6)$$

$$M_3 = \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} s G_{ijkl}(x, s) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y_j} d\Omega \quad (7)$$

Here, variables with \sim show that they are Laplace transformed, and s is the transformed parameter.

Each coefficient of ε in Eq. (4) must approach zero identically such that the equality is true for all values of ε . Considering the coefficient of ε^{-1} and ε^0 , the following equations can be obtained.

$$s \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) \left[\frac{\partial u_k^1(x, y, s)}{\partial y_l} + \frac{\partial u_k^0(x, s)}{\partial x_l} \right] \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y_j} d\Omega = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} s G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) \left(\frac{\partial u_k^1(x, y, s)}{\partial x_l} + \frac{\partial u_k^2(x, y, s)}{\partial y_l} \right) \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y_j} d\Omega + \\ & \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} s G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) \left(\frac{\partial u_k^0(x, s)}{\partial x_l} + \frac{\partial u_k^1(x, y, s)}{\partial y_l} \right) \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} f_i v_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \tilde{t}_i v_i d\Gamma \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\frac{\partial u_k^1}{\partial x_l}(x, y, s)$ is supposed as the following expression

$$u_k^1(x, y, s) = -\Phi(y, s) \frac{\partial u_k^0(x, s)}{\partial x_l} \quad (10)$$

Here, $\Phi(y, s)$ is the Y-periodic components of the characteristic function in the Laplace transformed domain.

Substituting Eq. (10) into Eq. (8), the following equation is obtained.

$$\int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} G_{ijkl}(x, s) \frac{\partial \Phi(y, s)}{\partial y_l} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y_j} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega^\varepsilon} G_{ijkl}(x, s) \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial y_j} d\Omega \quad (11)$$

Then, $\Phi(y, s)$ in the Laplace transformed domain can be obtained by solving Eq. (11).

Substituting Eq. (10) into Eq. (9), the governing equation for the macroscale problem can be obtained.

$$\int_{\Omega^e} s \left[G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) - G_{ijmn}(x, y, s) \frac{\partial \Phi_m^{kl}(y, s)}{\partial y_n} \right] \frac{\partial u_k^0(x, s)}{\partial x_l} \frac{\partial v_i}{\partial x_j} d\Omega = \int_{\Omega^e} f_i v_i d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma} \tilde{t}_i v_i d\Gamma \quad (12)$$

Taking the volume average by $f^H = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y f dy$, the effective relaxation tensor G_{ijkl}^H in the Laplace transformed domain can be written as

$$G_{ijkl}^H(x, s) = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y \left[G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) - G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) \frac{\partial \Phi(y, s)}{\partial y_l} \right] dy \quad (13)$$

Considering Eq. (10) and Eq. (2), the microscopic stress vector $\sigma_{ij}^0(x, y, t)$ in the Laplace transformed domain is calculated.

$$\sigma_{ij}^0(x, y, s) = s \left[G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) - G_{ijkl}(x, y, s) \frac{\partial \Phi(y, s)}{\partial y_l} \right] \frac{\partial u_k^0(x, s)}{\partial x_l} \quad (14)$$

2.2 Multi-scale viscoelastic model of 3D braided composites

The 3D braided composite studied in the present work has a periodic microstructure, and the schematic of a multi-scale model for 3D four-directional braided composites is shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Multiscale analysis model of 3D four-directional braided composites

A bottom-up homogenization procedure is employed, which considers three scales (micro-scale fiber/matrix, meso-scale unit cell and macro-scale whole composite structure). First, analysis at the fiber/matrix scale is carried out for predicting the viscoelastic properties of the yarns. Conventional 3D braided composites consist of three kinds of cells, i.e., interior cells, surface cells, and corner cells [19]. In order to simplify the problem, only the interior cells are considered as RUCs in this study. The viscoelastic responses of meso-scale unit cells are calculated based on the predicted properties of the

yarns and matrix. Finally, the viscoelastic behaviors of the macroscale homogeneous composite model are derived from the predicted properties of the meso-scale interior unit cells.

2.3 Finite element formulation of the homogenized properties

In order to analyze the viscoelastic behavior of 3D braided composites, a micro-scale representative volume element (RVE) for yarns and a meso-scale RUC are firstly established. It is important to note that the homogenized effective relaxation tensor and stress vector in microscopic and mesoscopic require the solution for the characteristic function $\tilde{\Phi}$.

The finite element discretized form of Eq. (11) for calculating the characteristic function $\tilde{\Phi}$ would be expressed as

$$K\Psi = F, \quad (15)$$

where

$$K = \int_Y B^T G B dY \quad (16)$$

$$F = \int_Y B^T G dY \quad (17)$$

Here, B is the shape function derivative matrix. G is the relaxation tensor matrix in Laplace transformed domain. Ψ is the discretized form of the corrector $\tilde{\Phi}$ with six columns. The right term of Eq. (15) is a matrix F with six load vectors, leading to the same number of equations that need to be solved.

2.3.1 Microscale effective relaxation modulus

In the present work, MPFE method [14] was used to calculate the matrix $\tilde{\Phi}$ in Eq. (15). In order to obtain the total effective stiffness matrix K_{micro} and equivalent nodal load matrix F_{micro} of the yarns, the micro-scale RVE is divided into three kinds of 20-node rectangular isoperimetric elements (as shown in Fig. 2). According to MPFE method, the effective relaxation modulus of the yarns in the Laplace transformed domain can be obtained.

Fig. 2 Mesh schemes of the different scales (a) the microscale RVE and three kinds of subcells, (b) the mesoscale RUC and three kinds of subcells

2.3.2 Mesoscale effective relaxation modulus

After obtaining the effective relaxation modulus of yarns in the Laplace transformed domain, the characteristic functions $\tilde{\Phi}$ for the mesoscale unit cell of 3D braided four-directional composites can

be calculated similar to that for the micro-scale RVE. Then the effective relaxation modulus for the mesoscale RUC can be determined.

3. Inverse Laplace transformation

In practice, it is necessary to solve the local problem in the Laplace transformed domain for several s due to the relaxation modulus is not separable with respect to the space and time variables. Thus, the rational curve-fitted and the inverse Laplace transform is required after computing. Assume that the viscoelastic properties of 3D braided composites satisfy the following three-parameter model [20], the form of the n -order Prony series can be expressed as follows

$$G(t) = G_{\infty} + \sum_{i=1}^n G_i e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}} \quad (18)$$

By using the Laplace transformation, Eq. (18) can be rewritten as

$$G(s) = \frac{G_{\infty}}{s} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{G_i}{s + \frac{1}{\tau_i}} \quad (19)$$

The parameters G_{∞} , G_i and $\frac{1}{\tau_i}$ are calculated by the numerical fitting of the least square method, the main expression can be written as

$$\min f(G_{\infty}, G_i, \frac{1}{\tau_i}) = \min \sum_{i=1}^n (\bar{G}(s) - G(s))^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n (\bar{G}(s) - \frac{G_{\infty}}{s} + \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{G_i}{s + \frac{1}{\tau_i}})^2 \quad (20)$$

Therefore, the equivalent relaxation modulus in the time domain can be expressed as Eq. (18) if the parameters G_{∞} , G_i and $\frac{1}{\tau_i}$ in Eq. (19) can be determined. Since the 3D braided composites are composed of two-phase materials, the first order Prony series is selected to fit the homogenized relaxation tensor and stress distribution in this work.

4. Numerical examples and discussions

4.1 Time-dependent homogenized properties of 3D braided composites

For 3D four-directional braided composites studied in this work, the matrix is epoxy resin ED-6 and the fiber is T300 carbon. The material parameters of the components used in the following simulation are given in Table 1.

Carbon fiber (T300)	Value	Epoxy resin (ED-6)	Value
Transverse modulus E_{f1} (GPa)	13.8	Elastic coefficient G_1 (GPa)	4.5

Longitudinal modulus E_{f3} (GPa)	220	Elastic coefficient G_2 (GPa)	0.34
Shear modulus G_{f13} (GPa)	9.0	Viscosity coefficient η_2 (GPa·h)	300
Shear modulus G_{f12} (GPa)	5.52	Volume modulus K (GPa)	5.56
Longitudinal poisson's ratio γ_{f12}	0.25		
Transverse poisson's ratio γ_{f31}	0.3		

Table1 Elastic constants of carbon fiber and viscoelastic constants of resin matrix [16].

4.1.1 Time-dependent homogenized properties of yarns

The effective relaxation modulus of yarns can be obtained by Eq. (13). Fig. 3 depicts the comparison of the homogenized creep compliances of the yarns evaluated in this work and calculated by Cai et al. [16]. It is noticed that there is a good agreement between the present results and the existing data in the literature.

Fig. 3 Effective creep compliances of yarns versus time.

Fig. 4 plots the effective relaxation modulus of the yarns with a constant fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 0.85$). It is found that the effective relaxation moduli G_{1111}^{HI} , G_{3333}^{HI} , G_{1212}^{HI} , G_{2323}^{HI} decrease monotonically with increase of time. On the contrary, the effective relaxation moduli G_{1112}^{HI} , G_{1113}^{HI} increase with increase of time, and they reach a steady state after 400 hours.

Fig. 4 Effective relaxation modulus of yarns versus time

4.1.2 Time-dependent homogenized properties of unit cells

The effective relaxation moduli of unit cells are calculated according to Eq. (13). Fig. 6 gives the effective relaxation modulus of the unit cells in the time domain with the fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 0.37$) for 3D braided composites. It is found that the effective relaxation moduli of the unit cells in the time domain are similar to the yarns. The mesoscale effective relaxation moduli G_{1111}^{H2} , G_{3333}^{H2} , G_{1212}^{H2} , G_{2323}^{H2} decrease monotonically with increase of time, and G_{1112}^{H2} , G_{1113}^{H2} increase with increase of time

Fig. 5 gives the effective relaxation moduli of the 3D braided composites with a constant fiber volume fraction ($V_f = 0.37$) and different braiding angles ($\varphi = 20^\circ : 50^\circ$) in the time domain. It can be found that the mesoscale effective relaxation moduli G_{1111}^{H2} , G_{1112}^{H2} , G_{1113}^{H2} , G_{1212}^{H2} , G_{2323}^{H2} increase monotonically with increase of the braiding angle while G_{3333}^{H2} decreases monotonically.

Fig. 5 Effective relaxation modulus of RUC for different braiding angles

4.2 Time-dependent stress of 3D braided composites

As an example, the time-dependent stresses of the 3D braided composite clamped-free beam with a certain forced displacement at the free edge are studied, as shown in Fig. 6. The dimension of the beam is $90 \times 20 \times 6$ mm, the forced displacement at the free edge is 10 mm.

Fig. 6 Sketch of clamped-free beam with a forced displacement

4.2.1 Time-dependent stress of the whole structure

Fig. 7 shows the time histories of macroscale time-dependent stresses σ_z in the time domain at position A (Fig. 6). It can be noted that the macroscale stresses decrease gradually in the time domain, and the stress relaxation behavior of 3D four-directional braided composites is completed by the combination of a shorter relaxation stage and a longer steady stage.

Fig. 7 Macroscale stress σ_z of a 3D braided composite beam versus time

4.2.2 Time-dependent stress of the unit cell

In order to further investigate the variation of stress with time, a detailed description for the mesoscale stress in a unit cell at time of 0h, 50h, 100h and 300h is presented, which is used to calculate the macroscale stress relaxation response for the position A. Due to the stress in Z-direction is dominant in the current boundary conditions, the mesoscale stress σ_z on the plane ($Z=0.5H$) is given in Fig. 8. It can be found that the mesoscopic stress gradually decreases with time increasing.

Fig. 8 Mesoscale stress σ_z on the plane $Z = H/2$ for a unit cell with different times.

4.2.3 Time-dependent stress of the yarn

The failure of 3D braided composites is commonly caused by the micro-destruction of fiber/matrix, therefore a further research on the relaxation stress in microscale is needed. As shown in Fig. 6, the mesoscale unit cell is firstly cut along the cross section of $Z=0.5H$, and then position B in the yarn is selected. Based upon the relaxation stress analysis results in macroscale and mesoscale, the microscale stresses at time $t=0h$, $t=100h$, $t=300h$ and $t=500h$ are calculated by homogenization method, as shown in Fig. 9. It can be found that there is a small variation for the microscale stress in 3-direction (fiber direction) as time increase, which means the viscoelastic properties in the microscale fiber/matrix model can be neglected at room temperature.

Fig. 9 Microscale stress σ_3 for a yarn with different times.

5. Conclusions

In this work, a new alternative TsFE calculation procedure for simulating the effective relaxation modulus and stress for 3D braided four-directional composites has been developed. The TsFE numerical model includes a homogeneous macroscale structure, a heterogeneous mesoscale unit cell and a heterogeneous microscale yarn. The viscoelastic behaviors of 3D braided composite clamped-free beams are predicted. The main conclusions can be listed as follows:

- (1) The viscoelastic properties of the 3D four-directional braided composites are obviously anisotropic.
- (2) The braiding angle and relaxation time are the important parameters affecting the viscoelastic properties of 3D four-directional braided composites. The 3D braided composites with smaller braiding angle have better relaxation-resistance abilities.
- (3) The stress distributions in a mesoscale unit cell and a microscale yarn show obvious inhomogeneity, especially at the interfaces of the structures.
- (4) Future work will focus on the asymptotic damage and strength analysis of 3D braided composites structures by considering the viscoelastic properties.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the National Natural Science Foundation of China (11432005), the R&D Cultivation Project of Heilongjiang Education Department (TSTAU-R2018001) and the Fundamental Research Foundation for Universities of Heilongjiang Province (JMRH2018XM01).

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